

Iteration 1: Lentune Bug Reproduction Process

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Overview of bug report workflow

This section describes the intended current (initial, before the first iteration of the action research cycle) bug report workflow at Lentune Ltd. An overview of the process is shown in Figure 1: Current bug report workflow (note that cards, issues and tickets are the same in the context of this work. Also, only some tickets are bug reports, while other tickets can be feature requests or tech debt items).

1. Problem Identification

The process begins with the identification of a problem by end users, internal team members, or developers:

- **Lentune end users:** Typically report issues via phone or email to the support team.
- **Lentune non-technical internal team members:** Raise problems through face-to-face discussions with the support team.
- **Lentune developers:** Directly create JIRA tickets if they encounter an issue during their work.

2. Initial Evaluation by Support Team

Upon receiving a problem report, the support team evaluates the issue:

- If the report comes from end users, it is logged into a HubSpot ticket for initial documentation.
- For reports from internal team members and HubSpot tickets logged, the support team creates a JIRA ticket if the problem needs further investigation.
- For reports from developers, a JIRA ticket is logged by the developers directly.

3. Grooming by Product Team

The product team grooms the problem reported in the JIRA ticket. This involves:

- Deciding whether the problem needs further technical analysis or can be resolved with existing knowledge.

- Reviewing and prioritizing the JIRA tickets to ensure that the minimum information requirement is met, and critical issues are addressed promptly.

4. Developer Diagnosis

Prioritized bug reports are placed on the developer JIRA board, where developers pick up tickets for diagnostic purposes. The developer's role includes:

- Attempting to understand the nature and underlying cause of bug report.
- Engaging in the bug reproduction process to validate the issue.

5. Bug Reproduction Process

This critical stage involves developers replicating the problem described in a bug report in a controlled environment:

- **Reproduce Problem Reported:** Developers follow the information or steps described in the bug report to see if the problem can be reproduced.
 - If the problem is reproduced successfully, the process moves to the bug fixing stage.
 - If the problem cannot be reproduced, developers need to identify any information gaps and move to step 6 to seeking help from other members such as reporter of the bug or other developer has better skill sets.

6. Information Gap Analysis

If there are gaps in the information provided:

- Developers seek to fill information gaps through further investigation or by reaching out for more detailed information. This can mean reaching out to the original card creator for more information. Some information can be obtained while others cannot be due to various reasons, such as changed data or reporters who are not reachable. Therefore, it may take a long time to obtain required information.
- Once the information gap is filled, the process will loop back to step 5 and developers attempt to reproduce the bug again.

7. Decision Point: Can Problem Be Reproduced?

- **Yes:** If the problem can be reproduced, the developer proceeds to the bug fixing stage.
- **No:** If the problem remains non-reproducible even after filling information gaps, it is marked as a non-reproducible bug. Further actions are deferred until more information becomes available or the issue reoccurs with better clarity. Additionally, if a bug is critical and urgent, the bug report will never be marked as not reproduceable until the problem is fully resolved.

Figure 1: Current bug report workflow

Current application monitoring setup

Application Insight: Lentune applications have Application Insights (a third-party product) built in. There are three parts of Lentune applications tracked by Application Insights:

- Client-end code: Lentune's client are single page applications in Type Script and HTML. The Application Insights is implemented by default as documented in [Microsoft Azure Monitor Application Insights JavaScript SDK - Azure Monitor | Microsoft Learn](#).
- Backend code: Lentune backend code is in C# .Net. Application Insight is set up as documented in [Application Insights for ASP.NET Core applications - Azure Monitor | Microsoft Learn](#)
- Infrastructure: Lentune's backend is hosted by Azure App Service. The infrastructure log also done by Applications Insights is documented in [Monitor Azure App Service - Azure App Service | Microsoft Learn](#)

Data to capture status quo of current process

Following data describes the status quo of the bug reproduction process as of 30th August 2024 , which includes:

- Number of bug reports created in last 90 days: **150**
- Number of bug reports marked as non-reproducible in the last 90 days: **28**
- Average closing time for bug reports closed in the last 30 days: **60 days**
- Average number of data items¹ provided in the bug report created in last 30 days: **2.3**
- Number of personnel involved in handling a bug report closed in the last 30 days: **(min 2, max 10, avg 6.2)**
- Number of interactions² per bug report for bug report closed in the last 30 days: **(min 1, max 18, avg 9.7)**
- Number of accesses to application monitoring (Application Insights) in the last 30 days: **3**

¹ A data item is a piece of information of an information type. For example, if a bug report includes setup information and Steps to reproduce then this bug report has 2 data items.

² Interactions can take in multiple form such as email, phone call even face to face discussion. Each email, phone call or face to face discussion counts as one interaction.

Data currently collected

The following section describes the data currently collected by Lentune to help with understanding bug reports submitted for Lentune applications. Some data collection is done with sampling, i.e., we collect only a subset of all data. More detail can be found in <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/azure-monitor/app/sampling-classic-api>.

Client-end data:

- Page view (sampled): Number of visits to a page. Collected data for each visit include: URL, Browser version, Country or region, State or province, City, Load time, refUri and duration.
- Requests (sampled): Number of requests sent from the client end. Collected data for each request include: Event time, Name, Response code, Successful request, Response time, URL and AspNetCoreEnvironment.

Backend data:

- Exception error log: Shows the details about the exceptions collected for the monitored application. Collected data for each log include: Event time, Message, Exception type, Failed method, URL and error message.
- Database access (sampled): Shows information about the database access of the monitored application. Collected data for each database access includes: Event time, Type, Call status, Duration and Name.

Infrastructure data:

- App Service Usage: Resource consumption of the monitored application. The data include: CPU usage (%), Memory usage (%), Data in/out (MB), Request count and Response time (ms).
- SQL Server Usage: Resource consumption of database used by the monitored application. The data include: CPU usage (%), Storage Usage (%) and Data I/O (MB).
- Blob storage access log: Access log of the blob storage system. The data include: Total egress/ingress (MB), Average latency (ms) and request result breakdown (success/fail).

Perceptions on current bug reproduction process

In this section, we present the insights from the interviews with different stakeholders about their understanding of the current bug reproduction process at Lentune Ltd as outlined above.

The people selected for interview are from the teams action on the bug reproduction process for diagnostic and fixing. Referring to the roles in the bug reproduction process outlined above this includes:

- **Lentune non-technical internal team members:** Customer support team (Gareth).
- **Lentune developers:** Alex, Marc

Section 1: General Information & Background with Bug Reproduction Process

- **Alex:** Software developer with two years of experience. Finds the bug reproduction process occasionally challenging, especially when bugs are related to specific application data in the context of the customer. For example, a bug may appear only when a certain values or value combinations are entered into the app that may be within or outside the allowed range.
- **Gareth:** Works in customer support with no formal software engineering background. Often needs detailed information from customers, as he has limited ability to reproduce complex bugs.
- **Marc:** Experienced developer (10 years) who prioritizes efficient reproduction techniques, often working around limitations in data available in bug reports and sometimes needing production-like environments of the application for bug reproduction and diagnostic.

Common Themes:

- All interviewees emphasized the importance of detailed information and accurate bug reports for successful bug reproduction.
- Experience levels influence their understanding of bug reproduction, with more experienced developers requiring less direct customer data.

Section 2: Experiences and Challenges with Current Bug Reproduction Process

- **Alex:** Describes issues with application data that are context specific and cases where UI-only bugs are hard to replicate. Emphasizes need for specific data for some bugs.
- **Gareth:** Struggles with incomplete customer information and uses screen sharing or customer-provided videos to understand bugs better.
- **Marc:** Notes challenges in distinguishing relevant data for bugs and occasionally requires a copy of the production database. He mentions difficulties with reproducing complex bugs involving several steps or specific conditions.

Common Themes:

- Reproducing data context specific bugs is challenging across roles.
- Communication with the initial bug reporter is vital for accurate reproduction.
- More experienced developers (like Marc) rely less on external information but still find that incomplete descriptions from customers can be a bottleneck.

Section 3: System Usability & Performance for Bug Reproduction

- **Alex:** Relies on developer tools like Chrome Developer Tools but is unfamiliar with advanced application monitoring tools.
- **Gareth:** Uses DataDog and finds it essential for understanding customer actions, though the data isn't always complete (such as lack of the environmental context in which users used the app or setup data) or relevant to the problem he has on hand. To locate the accurate information is time consuming in some case.
- **Marc:** Prefers using SQL to query monitoring data directly rather than DataDog, indicating that he finds application monitoring tools somewhat inefficient for his needs.

Common Themes:

- DataDog is useful but can be time-consuming or limited depending on the user's familiarity with it.
- Each respondent highlighted different application monitoring tools or logs, reflecting their roles and preferences in accessing debug information.

Section 4: Integration and Compatibility with Application Monitoring Systems

- **Alex:** Has not fully explored integration with application monitoring tools due to limited usage.
- **Gareth:** Relies on DataDog and occasionally finds integration issues where the customer setup differs.
- **Marc:** Feels confident in integrating and using SQL over other tools, suggesting that he prefers a more hands-on approach for compatibility issues.

Common Themes:

- Experience with monitoring systems varies greatly, with more technical roles gravitating toward SQL and manual checks.
- Compatibility concerns are generally addressed by those with more technical experience.

Section 5: Overall Satisfaction with Bug Reproduction and Monitoring Process

- **Alex:** There is no comment from Alex as he is not using the APM currently.
- **Gareth:** Rates his satisfaction at around 7 out of 10, mainly due to delays from incomplete information.
- **Marc:** Satisfied and considers his current process effective, valuing the ability to access production data safely.

Common Themes:

- Overall satisfaction is moderate, with all participants recognizing areas for improvement, particularly in data accessibility and communication.

Section 6: Additional Comments and Suggestions

- **Alex:** There is no comment from Alex as he is not using APM currently.
- **Gareth:** Wants clearer customer instructions to avoid back-and-forth communication.
- **Marc:** Emphasizes the need for complete screenshots and thorough bug report details.

Analysis of interview result

- **Commonalities:** All participants highlighted the necessity of detailed bug reports, efficient data access, and accurate reproduction steps. They shared frustration with incomplete information and expressed a need for improvement in data handling and application monitoring usage.
- **Differences:**
 - **Role-Based Approach:** Developers (Alex and Marc) rely more on technical tools (SQL, Developer Tools), while customer support (Gareth) leans on DataDog and customer-provided data.
 - **Experience Level:** Marc's advanced experience shows in his confidence with direct SQL usage and minimal reliance on third-party monitoring, whereas Alex and Gareth rely more on available tools or communication with customers.
 - **Tool Preference:** Marc favors SQL over application monitoring tools, while Gareth finds DataDog helpful but sometimes limited.

Potential improvement for the bug reproduction process

In this section we discuss the potential improvements we can make to bug reproduction at Lentune in two aspects: (1) data gaps to fill and (2) process change can be made.

Information gaps to fill

Below we list types of data that would help fill current information gaps (as identified in the interviews above). Some of these information gaps were also identified in our previous work: We use tag S1 for [information gap] and S2 for study [APM]

Client-end:

- **End-user Action Tracking Data (S1, S2):** full logs of actions, URLs, timestamp, screens accessed and session replay. This gap is mentioned in *Section 2: Experiences and Challenges with Current Bug Reproduction Process*
- **Context and Environment Data (S1):** system configurations and version numbers of software users use with the application. This gap is mentioned in *Section 3: System Usability & Performance for Bug Reproduction*
- **Expected Outcomes Data (S1):** expected outcome for end user for a specific action or task. This is not directly mentioned in the interviews, but Interviewees

keep mentioned using further communication with customers to find out what user trying to achieve.

- **Error and Running Log Data (S1, S2):** data about the error at the front end and the console log when bug happens. This data gap is mentioned in *Section 3: System Usability & Performance for Bug Reproduction* by multiple interviewees.

Backend:

- **Database Log Data:** database transactions that were running when the bug occurred. This data gap is mentioned in *Section 2: Experiences and Challenges with Current Bug Reproduction Process*
- **Third-Party Integration Logging Data:** data about third party applications, such as end point is called, parameters used for external requests, response of the external request. This gap is identified by the main researcher when looking at the backend errors logged in the Lentune ticket system.
- **Enhanced Error Logs and Stack Traces Data (S1, S2):** full error messages and stack trace with contextual information. This gap is identified by the main research's analysis based on the interview data and data in Lentune's ticket system.

Infrastructure:

The following gaps in the infrastructure are identified by the main researcher based on the experience and understanding of Lentune's applications and processes.

- **Resource usage data:** data about the resource utilization of infrastructure items, e.g., CPU and RAM usage when bug occurred.
- **Release and deployment log data:** data about when the application is deployed and released, e.g., the date, time and the scope (functionalities included) of the release.
- **Network traffic analysis data:** This data is about to understand the network traffic when bug happened. For example, if there is any anomaly access when bug happened.

Bug reproduction process improvements

Following are some recommendations for the bug reproduction process improvements for Lentune Ltd.

- **Enhance the Data Access System Usability:** Feedback indicates that the current system for querying application monitoring data is not sufficiently intuitive, which can lead to inefficiencies in bug reproduction. Improving the

interface for querying data—such as adding clearer search filters, simplifying navigation, and offering more descriptive labels—would help team members quickly locate relevant logs and performance metrics, streamlining the troubleshooting process.

- **Provide Comprehensive Training on Application Monitoring for Bug Reproduction:** Users may not be fully leveraging the available application monitoring data to reproduce bugs effectively. Structured training sessions that cover best practices, tips for identifying relevant logs, and examples of successful bug reproduction using the monitoring data will equip users with the necessary skills. Ongoing support, such as quick-reference guides or an FAQ, could further empower the team in their daily troubleshooting tasks.
- **Refine the Bug Report Template for More Relevant Information:** To facilitate more accurate and complete reports, the bug report template should guide users to include all necessary information for reproduction. This might include sections for detailing the environment (browser, OS version, etc.), steps leading to the issue, any error messages encountered, and a dedicated field for attaching screenshots or logs. By encouraging thorough and consistent reporting, the development team can address issues more effectively, reducing the need for follow-up and expediting resolution.

Action Points Planned for the next study cycle

Following are the action points that the Lentune development team decided to take in the next study cycle to improve the intervention. The decision is based on potential improvements outlined above and the resources Lentune has for the project of improve bug reproduction cycle. Improvements address two aspects: closing information gaps and enhancing the bug reproduction process. It should be noted that the following section focuses on the overarching objectives rather than the specifics of implementation and results.

Close Information Gaps

Client-end data:

- **Time stamp when bug happened:** We will add a requirement for the time stamp for when the bug happened in the bug report template to provide information to our team to help with locating time related data (sources for that data are to be determined).
- **URL of the page where bug occurred:** We will add a requirement for the URL of the application page where a client end error happened. This information will also help Lentune team members to locate relevant information quickly.

- **User action data:** Lentune currently use DataDog to track users' action, however due to the cost and overhead, Lentune only tracks selected users. We will further enhance this data type collection to cover more users.
- **Expected outcome data:** We will add a requirement for bug reports to include the expected outcomes of an action for customers, so the Lentune team can understand the problem better.

Back-end Data:

- **Third party integration log:** Lentune will enhance the logging of data exchanged with external systems.

Infrastructure Data:

- **SQL transaction Data:** Lentune will start to log SQL transactions of its database used by the application.

Enhance Bug Reproduction Process

Based on the feedback from *Section 2: Experiences and Challenges with Current Bug Reproduction Process*. Lentune will investigate how internal log interface can be improved to make it easier to use for all the people involved in the bug reproduction process.

Lentune will also enhance the training for application monitoring usage for the people involved for bug reproduction process based on the feedback received in Section 3: System Usability & Performance for Bug Reproduction.

Note for action study iterations and addressed issues

In the following iterations of this action research study, we will keep improving the bug reproduction process of Lentune. The gaps identified during each iteration of the action research cycle will be added to a pool (backlog) of issues that we can address. We then will select issues to be implemented in different iterations (and regardless of the iteration in which the issues were identified) based on (1) their potential to improve the bug reproduction process, (2) the resource available in the Lentune development team and (3) priority of the company. Some issue may not be addressed at the end of this study. However, we aim to address the most significant issues and also those that will lead to significant improvements (i.e., at the end of the study we hope to achieve a plateau). Also, process improvement in general is a continuous activity and Lentune will keep reviewing and addressing the issues in the pool (backlog) even after this study concludes.

The backlog can be found in [TaskBackLog.xlsx](#). The backlog contains the following information for the workable items:

- **Category:** The category to which the workable item belongs (e.g., Close Information Gap, Enhance Bug Reproduction Process).
- **Id:** A unique identifier for the workable item.
- **Item Detail:** Detailed information about the workable item.
- **Identified Stage:** The stage of the study at which the workable item was initially identified.
- **Attempt Stages:** The stages of the study in which a workable item is addressed, i.e., when the implementation is planned, completed and when feedback about the modified intervention is collected and analyzed (i.e., a complete cycle). This can spread over multiple stages and the last stage mentioned is the stage in which the item is to be completed.